

Research Article

Enhancement of mechanical properties of Q-235 high strength steel using heat treatment process

Muhammad Imran^{1*}, Muhammad Imran Lashari¹, Muhammad Amir Shahzad¹, Muhammad Ahmed Khan², Mirza Muhammad Abubakar Baig³, Saeed Jamal¹

¹Mechanical Engineering Department, NED, University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

²Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Engineering and Technology, Lahore, Pakistan

³Mechanical Engineering Department, The University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

***Corresponding author.**

Email address: imranshabbir0000@gmail.com

Accepted: 10 April, 2020; **Online:** 17 April, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3753646>

Abstract: Heat Treatment behavior of Q235 high strength steel (HSS) for structural engineering application has been an important research topic in recent years. In this research, a review of high strength steel (HSS) behavior before and after heat treatment is provided. In this study first of all mechanical properties like Ultimate Tensile strength, Yield Strength, Toughness and Hardness are calculated before heat treatment and then performed heat treatment processes like Annealing, Hardening and Tempering and recalculate all above mentioned mechanical properties. As a result, the Ultimate Tensile Strength was increased from 347 MPa to 883 MPa, the Yield Strength was increased from 240 MPa to 750 MPa, the Hardness was increased from 105BHN to 238BHN and the Impact Toughness was lowered. It can be seen that heat treatment process greatly improves the mechanical properties of high strength steel. Therefore, the heat treatment has the advantage that the performance of material can be easily improved without changing the specimen size. In the future, a microstructure analysis of this study can also be performed.

Keywords: High Strength Steel, Heat Treatment, Mechanical Properties

1. Introduction

From 1960-1990, ASTM A36 (with a nominal yield strength of 248MPa/36ksi) was the predominant structural steel used for building construction while high-strength low-alloy quenched and tempered alloy steels (with nominal yield strength that changes from 248-690MPa/50-100ksi) were used in specific applications alternatively. In USA ASTM A-992 taken in 1998 is recently the most common use of steel for (W-shaped) sections [1]. The high strength steel (HSS) whose nominal yield strength, is greater than 460 MPa/67 ksi, is allowed to use in special characteristics, like long-span bridges and high-rise buildings. When separated with conventional steel, the construction structure using high-strength steel (HSS) offers high-strength advantages and reducing weight, which can lead to the construction economy. As a result of research on the behalf of application and behavior of high strength steel (HSS), is an important topic in the community of structural engineering [2-4].

History clearly shows that the threat of fire has a significant influence to the unification of structure in its life time. In spite of the fact that most steel structures can face fire or exposure, although there is no ideological damage after the fire exposure, later fire elements can face residual stresses and deformation during the cooling process [5]. Study on High Strength Steel (HSS) behavior before and after fire exhibition has been carry out by various research workers in which they analyze residual strength and fire resistance of the High Strength Steel (HSS) structure [6]. A comprehensive overview on the response of high strength steel (HSS) before or after high temperature exhibition, containing mechanical behavior of various types of stresses generated in high temperature execution of high strength steel (HSS).

Steel with compounds, such as Molybdenum (Mo), Chromium (Cr), Vanadium (V), Niobium (Nb), and Titanium (Ti) can cure carbides during heat treatment, and these carbides also contribute a vital role in finding their properties [7-9]. Morphology, the size and structure of steel-growing prescriptions, were featured by SEM and TEM. There is a common way of Electrolytic extraction that separates the precipitated stages of steel. The inspection of XRD and the formerly mentioned techniques can be submitted for the examination. Extracted precipitates also permit suitable examination of the 3-dimensional morphology of precipitated stages [10].

In the progress and use of ocean resources underwater pipelines is recently the most systematic and inexpensive means of transferring oil and natural gas from deep water to seaward facilities.

In designing submarine pipes, it is often needed that the design should be very safe, light weight, high cost savings and have low environmental impact. To meet the demand, micro alloy ultra-high strength steel is used as a material for submarine pipes. Similarly, the enhancement of strength in steel usually helps in the failure of induced stress cracking, fracture toughness, and formability [11-14]. In every structure where high strength steel is used the higher strength of this grade is attractive to reduce the mass by reducing thickness. This high strength helps in improvement of safety protection requirements so that mass increases are reduced. Apart from high strength, in some particular grades of high strength steel (HSS) the absorption of energy is possible [15-16]. The problem of specific engineering and production system will be resolved, which will help to design more powerful engineering solutions of high strength steel (HSS) applications with abandoned tools [17-18].

In this paper, Q-235 steel is used for the heat treatment process which is a Chinese steel grade of ordinary carbon-structured steel containing the density of material 7.85 grams/cm³. This material is divided into four quality grades: Q-235A Steel, Q-235B Steel, Q-235C Steel and Q-235D Steel, where “Q” stands for Yield Strength, and “235” is that Yield Strength value (235 MPa), and Tensile Strength is 370 to 500 MPa, test is conducted on 16mm diameter steel bar or steel plate. Q-235 material is mostly rolled into round steel, wire rod, square steel, I-beam, flat steel, steel channel, steel plate, steel section and steel angle, etc. Q-235 steel is extensively used in construction and engineering structures. It can also be used to manufacture steel bars or to make factory house frames, bridges, transmission towers, vehicles, containers, boilers, ships, etc.

2. Materials and methods

Initially mechanical properties of Q235 high strength steel are calculated by using UTM machine then selected heat treatment cycles are performed according to ASTM A858/A858M. There have been many experiments completed during this study to obtain the optimized results throughout the process. Subsequently, the mechanical properties are calculated after the applied heat treatment process. The mechanical properties provide a good analysis of the determined results in the entire experimental study. The heat treatment process and cycles used throughout the study are described in details in the Figure. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of heat treatment process and cycles

The comprehensive composition and grades of high strength steels used in the study for the heat treatment process has been shown in Table. 1.

Table 1: Q235 Composition of high strength steel

Names	Grades	Chemical Composition in percentage				
		C	Mn	S	Si	P
Q-235	A	0.14-0.22	0.30-0.65	0.3	0.05	0.045
	B	0.12-0.20	0.30-0.70	-	0.045	
	C	≤ 0.18	0.35-0.80	-	0.04	0.04
	D	≤ 0.17	-	-	0.35	0.035

2.1 Heat treatment cycles

i. Annealing Cycle:

- Heated the material to a critical point which is 810°C.
- Soaked at that temperature for 10 minutes for tensile specimen and 20 minutes for impact specimen depending on the thickness.
- Cooling takes place in the furnace itself.

ii. Hardening Cycle:

- Heated the material above critical temperature which is 830°C.
- Soaked at that temperature for 10 minutes for tensile specimen and 20 minutes for impact specimen depending on the thickness.

iii. Tempering Cycle:

- Heated the material at four different tempering temperatures (300°C, 350°C, 400°C, 450°C) respectively.
- Soaked at that temperature for 10 minutes for tensile specimen and 20 minutes for impact specimen depending on the thickness.
- Cooling takes place at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Brinell hardness test (ASTM E10 standard)

Brinell hardness number is defined as “ratio of applied load in Newton’s to the surface area of impression”.

$$\text{B.H.N} = \frac{\text{Load in Newtons}}{\text{Surface area of impression}}$$

The value of Brinell hardness test before the heat treatment was 105 BHN. When heat treatment was performed the annealed sample has a hardness value of 92.7 BHN, hardened sample has a value of 238.3 BHN and respectively the tempering was performed at four different temperatures such as 300°C, 350°C, 400°C and 450°C and the obtained hardness values were 238.2 BHN, 196.8 BHN, 180 BHN, and 165.27 BHN respectively. Effect of tempering temperature on the hardness of material is shown in the Figure. 2.

Figure 2: Effect of tempering temperature on the hardness of material

3.2 Charpy Testing (Testing done on V-notch Charpy)

Impact test is used to determine the toughness of the material. In this study from the impact tests, the charpy impact tests are mainly selected for the metals, but also this is used in (i) Polymers (ii) Ceramics and (iii) Composites respectively. The charpy impact test is used to find out the impact toughness or simply toughness of a material. The charpy impact method is a high strain rate test that finds the absorbed energy during material failure/fracture. 55 * 10 * 10 mm is the ASTM E23 standard used for charpy impact test. This sample has notch on one of its larger face. The V type notch has a 2 mm deep notch with an angle of 45 degrees and 0.25 radiuses along the bottom. Figure 3 shows the schematic diagram for the charpy testing sections during the experiments.

Figure 3: Schematic of charpy testing

Formerly for the heat treatment process, the toughness value was 1003 KJ/m² but as tempered the specimen at four different tempering temperature like 300°C, 350°C, 400°C and 450°C the toughness values came out to be 262 KJ/m², 346 KJ/m², 671 KJ/m² and 970 KJ/m² respectively. Similarly the effect of tempering temperature before the treatment and after the treatment is shown in the Figure 4 on the hardness of material.

Figure 4: Effect of tempering temperature on the hardness of material

3.3 Tensile Test

Clamp one piece of any material at each end and draw it away from each other till its breakdown. This calculates how elastic its strength and stiffness put impact on the material during tensile testing. Figure 5 shows the schematic of ASTM E8M Standard for tensile test.

Figure 5: Schematic of ASTM E8M Standard for tensile test

Figure 6: Graphical representation b/w applied tensile stress and strain

The value of ultimate tensile strength before heat treatment was 347 MPa but as it is tempered then the specimen at four different tempering temperature such as 300°C, 350°C, 400°C and 450°C respectively obtained the ultimate tensile strength values obtained to be 822 MPa, 883 MPa, 698 MPa and 648 MPa respectively. Similarly the Table 2 provides the detailed results and properties and behavior of materials during tensile testing. Figure 7 described the effect of tempering temperature on the yield strength of material and the ultimate tensile strength materials. The graphical expressions described that if the tempering temperature increased throughout the heat treatment process then the yield strength would be higher. The temperature and the yield strength have the direct relationship.

Table 2: The properties and behavior of materials during tensile testing

Properties vs Behavior	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Impact Toughness (KJ/m ²)	Hardness No
Before Heat Treatment	240	347	1003	105
Tempered at 300°C	618	822	262	238.2

Tempered at 350°C	730	883	346	196.8
Tempered at 400°C	580	698	671	180
Tempered at 450°C	514	648	970	165.27

Figure 7: Effect of tempering temperature on the yield strength of material

4. Conclusion

The behavior of Q235 high strength steel (HSS) using heat treatment process for structural engineering application has been an important research topic in recent years. In this research, study about all heat treatment processes as well as how to perform different heat treatment process are done and how the mechanical properties vary before and after heat treatment process. In this regard, first of all mechanical properties like Ultimate Tensile Strength, Toughness, Hardness and Yield strength are calculated before heat treatment process and then performed different heat treatment processes using ASTM standards and after that recalculated all above mentioned mechanical properties. As a result, the Ultimate Tensile Strength increased from 347 MPa to 883 MPa, the Yield Strength increased from 240 MPa to 750 MPa, the Hardness increased from 105 to 238 and the Impact Toughness was lowered. In addition, when tempered the specimen at four different temperatures (300°C, 350°C, 400°C, 450°C) then a best result of Ultimate Tensile Strength (883MPa) and Yield Strength (730MPa) were at 350°C if toughness of

material is not required after that as the tempering temperature increases these properties starts to decrease while hardness has a best value at 300°C after this temperature it's also starts to decreases. But if toughness of material is necessary then the best value is at 450°C. In the future, a microstructure analysis of this study can also be performed.

Acknowledgements

All the praises and thanks are to Allah Almighty. Much appreciation to NED, University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan and Professor Maaz Akhtar for his supervision, guidance, and recommendations.

References

- [1]. Gustafson K, "Steel wise Evaluation of existing structures" Modern Steel Construction pp: 3. (2007).
- [2]. Qu L, Li H "Study on strength of Q420 steel section at elevated temperature" Fire Science and Technology 5: 223-225, (2004).
- [3]. Wang WY, Liu B, Kodur V, "Effect of temperature on strength and elastic modulus of high strength steel" Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering 25: 174-182, (2012).
- [4]. Wang WY, Liu B, Li GQ, "Experimental study on mechanical properties of Q460 high strength steel at elevated temperature" Journal of Disaster Prevention and Mitigation Engineering 35: 30-35, (2012).
- [5]. Makelainen P, Outinen J, Kesti J, "Fire design model for structural steel S420M based upon transient-state tensile test results" Journal of Constructional Steel Research 48: 47-57,(1998).
- [6]. Outinen J, Mäkeläinen P, "Mechanical properties of structural steel at elevated temperatures and after cooling down" Fire and Materials 28: 237- 251, (2004).
- [7] R.C. Thomson, H.K.D.H. Bhadeshia, "Changes in chemical composition of carbides in 2.25Cr-1Mo power plant steel" Mater. Sci. Technol. 10, 193-204(1994).
- [8] M.A. Islam, J.F. Knott, P. Bowen, "Kinetics of phosphorus segregation and its effect on low temperature fracture behavior in 2.25Cr-1Mo pressure vessel steel" Mater. Sci. Technol. 21,76-84 (2005).
- [9] K. Miyata, T. Kushida, T. Omura, Y. Komizo, "Coarsening kinetics of multicomponent MC-type carbides in high-strength low-alloy steels" Metall. Mater. Trans. A 34, 1565-1573,(2003).

- [10] Z.F. Hu, Z.G. Yang, “An investigation of the embrittlement in X20CrMoV12.1 power plant steel after long-term service exposure at elevated temperature” *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 383, 224-228,(2004).
- [11] F.R. Beckitt, “The formation of sigma-phase from delta-ferrite in a stainless steel” *ISIJ* 207 632-638.18,(1969).
- [12] T.P.S. Gill, J.B. Gnanamoorthy, “A method for quantitative analysis of delta-ferrite, sigma and M₂₃C₆ carbide phases in heat treated type 316 stainless steel weldments” *J. Mater. Sci.* 17 1513-1518,(1982).
- [13] J.M. Leitnaker, R.L. Klueh, W.R. Laing, “The composition of eta carbide phase in 21/4Cr-1Mo steel” *Metall. Trans. A* 6, 1949-1955,(1975).
- [14] A. Baltušnikas, R. Levinskas, “XRD analysis of carbide phase in heat resistant steels” *Mater. Sci.*12, 192-198,(2006).
- [15]. Lange J, Wohlfeil N, “Examination of the mechanical properties of steel S460 for fire” *Journal of Structural Fire Engineering* 1: 189-204, (2010).
- [16]. Qiang X, Bijlaard FSK, Kolstein H, “Deterioration of mechanical properties of high strength steel S460N under steady state fire condition” *Materials & Design* 36: 438-442, (2012).
- [17]. Qiang X, Bijlaard FSK, Kolstein H, “Deterioration of mechanical properties of high strength steel S460N under transient state fire condition” *Materials & Design* 40: 521-527, (2012).
- [18]. Qiang X, Bijlaard FSK, Kolstein H, “Elevated-temperature mechanical properties of high strength structural steel S460N: Experimental study and recommendations for fire-resistance design” *Fire Safety Journal* 55: 15-21, (2012).

Dedication

Special thanks and dedication to my friend Mr. ZESHAN ABBAS

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. *TWASP, NY, USA*. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>